

Characterization of AC-DC Transfer Shunts up to 100 A at 100 kHz Using Two-Stage, Amplifier-Aided Current Transformers

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Abstract— We describe the construction of two-stage, amplifier-aided current transformers (CTs) and their use to characterize AC-DC transfer shunts up to 100 A at 100 kHz. Tests show that the frequency coefficients of the CTs have small changes with current level. This level independence of the frequency coefficients for the CTs is used to characterize the frequency coefficients of the shunts up to 100 A and out to 100 kHz in terms of measurements at 20 A.

Keywords- Shunt; AC-DC; Transfer; Current; Transformer

I. INTRODUCTION

NIST is now offering broadband, ac-dc difference calibrations of current shunts up to 100 A at 100 kHz. We describe the in-house construction of two-stage, amplifier-aided current transformers (CTs) and a method to use the CTs to characterize AC-DC transfer shunts up to 100 A at 100 kHz. Tests show that the frequency coefficients of the CTs have small changes with current level. This level independence of the frequency coefficients for the CTs is used to characterize the frequency coefficients of the shunts up to 100 A and out to 100 kHz in terms of measurements at 20 A. Tests also show that, for well constructed shunts, the change in ac-dc transfer difference with current level below 100 Hz is small. We characterize the shunts by combining the ac-dc transfer differences at low frequency with the frequency coefficients of the CT. Other laboratories have characterized 100 A transfer shunts using calculable designs and build-up techniques [1,2,3]. One advantage of this method is that it is suitable for characterization of shunts whose structure is not calculable or suitable for simulation.

II. CONSTRUCTION OF CTs

Current transformers provide a useful means of scaling higher levels of current to lower levels of current that can then be measured by monitoring the voltage drop across a secondary burden resistance. They also have the inherent advantage of providing good isolation and rejection of common-mode voltages developed across multiple current sensing devices. Most ordinary current transformers exhibit relatively large errors, which are critical functions of the operating current, secondary burden, and frequency. However, the work done by Souders [4,5] showed that amplifier-aided multistage current transformers could achieve very high accuracies over the frequency range of 50 Hz to 10 kHz. Furthermore, the change in ratio over a wide range of frequencies, i.e. the frequency

coefficients, would be expected to be small with changes in current level.

The NIST Model DR 10/100 current transformer is a dual range, 2-stage, amplifier-aided, wide-band current transformer containing a built-in precision 1-ohm burden resistor that provides a voltage output proportional to the primary current. The design is a “through primary circuit” which conveniently allows other devices to be placed in series with the primary circuit. The nominal sensitivity of the transformer assembly is 10 mV/A on the 100 A range and 100 mV/A on the 10 A range. Because the units have built-in burden resistors with potential terminals, it is also possible to define the quantity trans-resistance of the CT as the magnitude of the output voltage, obtained on the potential connector, divided by the magnitude input current applied to the current terminals. The circuit for the CT in Fig. 1 includes the three windings, burden resistor, unloading amplifier and the polarity splitting amplifier, which is used to allow the convenience of just a single battery.

Fig.1. The CT windings and amplifier circuits showing I_p , I_s , and I_t , which are the primary, secondary, and tertiary currents respectively.

Fig. 2. Photograph of CT with 10 A and 100 A primary connections displayed.

Fig.3. Drawing of assembled CT housing.

The tertiary portion of the transformer was constructed by winding 100 turns of #18 awg magnet wire equally distributed around a high permeability, laminated core. A second high permeability, laminated core is stacked on top of the tertiary wound core. The secondary winding is formed by winding 100 turns of #18 awg magnet wire equally distributed around the stacked core assembly. The entire core assembly is held in place with glass type insulating tape. The core assembly is housed in an aluminum cylinder with end plates that have male and female type LC connectors that act as the input and output terminals. A rod from the center pin of each of the connectors through the center opening of the cores acts as a one-turn primary circuit. The return current is conducted back through the housing to the shell of the connector. The transformer is a through device allowing another current sensing device (shunt or transformer) to be placed in series.

III. MEASUREMENT METHOD

The method for characterization of transfer shunts at frequencies up to 100 kHz at 100 A involves two comparison steps as diagrammed in Fig. 4. The procedure normally includes the characterization of a reference standard shunt, or it can be

applied to the unit under test directly if it has suitable characteristics. In the first step, the ac-dc differences for a reference standard shunt are measured at 20 A for frequencies of 1 kHz or below. AC current shunts of good electrical and thermal design can be expected to exhibit small changes in AC-DC difference as a function of current level at frequencies of 1 kHz and below. The reference shunt in use at NIST has a design with small inductance and low skin effect. The parasitic inductances and capacitances are small and their changes with level at frequencies below 1 kHz are quite small. A large, distributed structure allows good thermal contact to heat sinks; therefore the temperature rise going from 20 A to 100 A is small. Measurements have shown that well constructed transfer shunts of varying designs have ac-dc transfer differences that track each other to better than 30 μ A/A up to 100 A at low frequencies. Therefore the ac-dc differences of the reference shunt are taken to be unchanged from the lower current levels up to the higher currents as given in the uncertainty section below. The shaded box on the left of Fig. 4 represents this part of the process. So if:

i = lower current level, j = higher current level
 ref = reference lower frequency

then:

$$\text{Shunt}(\delta)_{\text{Freq} = ref}^{Current = j} = \text{Shunt}(\delta)_{\text{Freq} = ref}^{Current = i}$$

In the second characterization step, the frequency coefficient for a two stage CT is characterized against a thermal transfer standard at 20 A using AC-AC difference measurements [6,7]. The dashed line in Fig. 4 represents this process.

Fig.4. Overall method for characterization of transfer shunts using CTs. Low frequency level independence of shunt is shown in shaded box. AC-DC characterization of shunt at 20 A is shown by dashed line. Higher frequency AC-AC characterization of shunt by CT is shown by solid lines.

Fig. 5. Circuit for connections of CT primary in series with test shunt. V_s and V_t are output voltages from CT and shunt, respectively.

From comparisons between different versions of the CTs, the AC-AC differences, or the frequency coefficients, of the CTs have been found to vary by less than $85 \mu\text{A/A}$ going from 20 A up to 100 A at 100 kHz, and much less at lower frequencies. The frequency coefficient for standard reference shunt is characterized against CT at each of the high current levels using AC-AC comparison. The solid lines in Fig. 4 represent this part of the process. So if:

f = measurement frequency, ref = reference lower frequency, then:

$$\text{Shunt}(\delta)_{\text{Freq} = f}^{\text{Current} = j} = \text{Shunt}(\delta)_{\text{Freq} = ref}^{\text{Current} = j} + \text{CT}(\delta)_{\text{AC}(ref) - \text{AC}(f)}$$

The circuit for the connection of the CT primary in series with the shunt under test is shown in Fig. 5. The tertiary winding and CT output amplifier are omitted for clarity. This configuration takes advantage of the inherent high common mode rejection properties of the transformer. It also reduces the chances of unwanted ground loops and reduces the requirement for good ac common-mode voltage rejection properties of the voltage measuring system. This consideration becomes particularly critical at high frequencies and high current. Common mode rejection can become a serious issue when the common mode voltages presented to each of the voltage measurement devices are not properly rejected.

IV. UNCERTAINTIES

The uncertainty contributions, in $\mu\text{A/A}$, for reference standard shunts are combined as the square root of the sum of the squares of the various components [8] and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. UNCERTAINTY CONTRIBUTIONS, IN $\mu\text{A/A}$, FROM THE VARIOUS CATAGORIES

Current (A)	1 kHz	10 kHz	30 kHz	70 kHz	100 kHz
Reference current converter standard					
20	20	20	20	40	57
Level dependence of shunt at low frequency					
50	15	15	15	15	15
100	30	30	30	30	30
Type A uncertainty for comparison of CT to thermal transfer standard					
20	1	1	2	2	2
Level dependence of CT frequency coefficient					
50	5	10	20	30	50
100	10	20	25	40	65
Comparison of Shunt to CT					
20	2	2	2	3	3
50	2	2	3	3	3
100	4	4	4	5	5
Uncertainty for reference standard shunt					
20	20	20	20	40	57
50	26	27	32	52	77
100	38	41	44	64	92
EXPANDED UNCERTAINTIES for Reference Standard Shunt ($k=2$)					
20	40	40	40	80	114
50	51	54	64	105	155
100	75	83	88	128	183

The uncertainty matrix contributions for the characterization of reference standard shunts include:

- The established uncertainties for the reference thermal transfer standard at 20 A.
- The level dependence of the high current shunt at low frequency, e.g. 1 kHz, as determined by comparison of shunts of totally different construction. These low frequency properties are expected to be level independent, so the variations observed are taken as uncertainty contributions.
- Type A uncertainty for comparisons between CTs and thermal transfer standard.
- Level dependence of the CT frequency coefficients as determined by comparison of multiple amplifier aided CTs.
- Type A uncertainty for comparisons between CTs and shunts.

As an overall test of the methods and uncertainties given in this work, the level variations between one of the CTs and the NIST coaxial transfer shunt were measured and are plotted in Fig. 6. The error bars shown are approximately equal to the expanded uncertainty offered for the calibration of a test shunt.

V. SUMMARY

We have described the construction of two-stage, amplifier aided current transformers, and we have presented a method to characterize transfer shunts at currents from 20 A to 100 A and up to 100 kHz using the CTs. The method relies on the small level dependence of the frequency coefficients of these CTs. We have presented an uncertainty summary with values which represent significant reductions in uncertainties for NIST calibrations of AC-DC transfer shunts at 100 A and 100 kHz.

Fig. 6. Level variations between NIST reference standard shunt and CT. Error bars are equal to expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) for shunt calibration.

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